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Esanov Azizbek Shermamat o`g`li

Termiz davlat universiteti

Elektron pochta manzili:

azizbekesanov97@gmail.com

LANGUAGE CHOICE IN DIPLOMATIC COMMUNICATIONS

ANNOTATION:

This article analyzes some of the ways to choose and use different languages in diplomatic communication. First of all, the concept of "diplomatic language" is clarified, and then 4 different ways of using language in diplomatic communication are considered. It then discusses why it is not possible to create a single universal language for diplomatic communication.

KEYWORDS:

- diplomacy, language choice, diplomatic communication, lingua franca, alternative language.
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Introduction.

In linguistics, the term "language in diplomacy" can, of course, be interpreted in several different ways. For example, A Dictionary of Diplomacy describes a diplomatic language as "... in the Ancient Near East this was Akkadian; in the European system it was first Latin and then French; and in today's world system it is English" [1, 67]. In particular, It is recognized as a mastered language in the form of speech "used by one nation, tribe, or other similar large groups" in particular. In this sense, we can say that French was primarily a diplomatic language in the first part of the twentieth century. Second, as a particular means of communicating the subtle demands of the diplomatic profession; for instance, one country's delegate spoke about the matter in a wholly non-diplomatic manner. The term could also refer to a distinctive

shape, manner, or tone of communication, such as that of ministers who use especially powerful language to express themselves. It can refer to the verbal or nonverbal expression of thoughts or feelings: sending weapons is a universal language.

All of these meanings, as well as maybe a few more, can be utilized in both spoken and written communication. It is essential in diplomacy to employ each of these meanings through language because language is not just a way of communicating ideas or communication, but it is also frequently the essence and foundation of diplomatic success.

Different ways of using language in diplomatic communication

We will start by looking at the most important components of diplomatic languages, such as the many ways in which language is utilized. Obviously, the first issue to address is establishing a shared language. Diplomats will be able to speak in only one language, which will be understood by all participants. This may be done between Germans and Austrians, Portuguese and Brazilians, officials of various Arab nations, British and Americans, and the like. Such instances are not only uncommon, but they frequently result in major disparities in the languages spoken in different countries. In the same way, English is spoken in the United Kingdom and India.

The challenge of communication between persons who speak different mother languages can be solved in a number of ways. While none of these strategies are perfect, it is beneficial to be aware of them. Of course, the first option is for one of the interlocutors to speak the other's language. This can cause a variety of issues: one party may lose their position owing to a lack of linguistic understanding while the other side gains an instantaneous advantage, resulting in unintended political repercussions, or it can cause various challenges in global diplomacy, and so on. The other alternative is for both parties to fully utilize a neutral third language. A significant issue is that both sides' lack of complete linguistic competence might lead to misunderstandings in mutual talks. Nonetheless, because of its political benefits, this strategy is frequently adopted in international practice. The third strategy, which involves the employment of interpreters, is commonly employed, particularly in multilateral diplomacy and high-level political talks. The fundamental reason for this approach's relative favour is not just mutual equality, but also the fact that politicians and government officials frequently lack foreign language skills. However, this procedure is also not without flaws: it is time-consuming, expensive, and occasionally inadequate or directly inaccurate. Because, "even if the translator has a good knowledge of both languages, he/she may not be familiar with the particular subject, which can be extremely specific - from the protection of the ozone layer to the homologation of sports records; it was not without reason that the slogan *traduttore - traditore*, translator - traitor, could be found in mediaeval Italy" [2, 42]. Charles Crawford explains the effects of foreign language knowledge and use in:

"You are always going to be more efficient if you can speak the language. Translators can get it wrong. People relax more when they are complaining away in their own language. You can go live on television if you are good enough, and present your policy to the general public" [3]

Finally, there is the possibility of using a single international synthetic, artificial language, such as Esperanto; this solution would have numerous benefits, but its implementation is unlikely in the near future, owing to the contradictions that dominate the international political, and thus the cultural and linguistic scene.

Discussion and results.

So, what is the best language to employ for diplomatic communication? The solution is far from straightforward. To begin with, the abovementioned statement cannot be considered as the final diplomatic language. Even if it was restricted to shared geographical regions or political group of nations, there were moments in the past when this or that language served as a common, widely utilized medium of interstate communication. Arguments like "clearer," "more flexible," "more expressive," "more fluent, delicate, or quiet," and "more suitable for international talks" have been used to persuade people to choose this or that language. The fact that so many languages have taken turns playing such a role throughout history indicates that linguistic or semantic considerations alone are insufficient. On the contrary, the dominance of one or more languages in diplomacy in international relations can be attributed to one or more powers' political, strategic, economic, cultural, or other superiority.

Let us give a very clear example, answering the question "What languages are required for a consultant at the embassy of a small European country in Vienna?" Presumably, if his professional activities are centred on business circles, the press, diplomatic activities, or cultural life, he must be proficient in German. Everyone speaks English and most speak French in the Austrian Ministry of Foreign Affairs in Ballhausplatz, but they really like hearing foreign diplomats speak fine German, especially because this is not the rough German of northern Germany, but a gentle and melodic Austrian German. Our colleague will require English, maybe French, and Russian to speak efficiently with other diplomats (depending on the diplomatic corps, he will be interested in communicating in the first place). If his job requires him to cover the operations of international organizations in Vienna, he will need to know English as well as French, Russian, Spanish, and maybe Arabic. This would be extremely useful to oil-exporting countries' organizations.

Many people choose a language to study and use as if their decision will inform them what they may anticipate from the market or the economy. This is an issue with language choice. To put it another way, people are occasionally compelled to acquire a language that will open doors to new economic, political, and market prospects. When it comes to language learning and usage, we are led by three principles: functionality, practicality and economy. However, other factors should be taken into consideration as well, primarily, non-market interests – cultural, intellectual, individual and societal factors [4, 4], that is, those factors that support multilingualism and that are reflected in it. As a result, it is evident that the solution to our query is not straightforward.

Conclusion.

Finally, the abovementioned diplomatic dialogue has its own advantages and disadvantages of using multiple languages, all of which optimize the impact of the oral or written text in foreign policy, increased awareness, more reliable results, and “talking to the interlocutor,” which is helpful in convincing or misleading him. Furthermore, diplomacy is built on talks and symbolizes communication between two or more governments [5, 3]. People comprehend foreign languages but feel their own, thus learning new languages can help us communicate more effectively with our negotiators.

In this case, knowing a language or languages and being able to use them effectively by selecting their acceptable option is not only an artistic skill, but also a requirement for a successful, professional diplomat to take greater responsibility for his demanding job of establishing mutually beneficial relationships between countries. In other words, our choice of language should be based on the quote by Nelson Mandela: “If you talk to a man in a language he understands, that goes to his head. If you talk to him in his language, that goes to his heart”.